

Synthesis, spectral, DFT calculations and biological activity studies of vanadyl complexes with L-aspartic acid and imidazoles/1,10-phenanthroline as co-ligands

R. N. Patel^{*a}, K. Maurya^a, Y. P. Singh^a, Y. Singh^a, S. Rather^a, A. Kamal^b and I. P. Tripathi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, A. P. S. University, Rewa-486 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : rnp64@ymail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, MGCGV, Chitrakoot, Satna-485 334, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Five vanadium(IV) complexes [VO(Aspa)(L)], where Aspa = L-aspartic acid, L = imidazole, 2-methylimidazole, 2-ethylimidazole, 2-methylbenzimidazole and 1,10-phenanthroline, have been synthesized and characterized by microanalysis, FTIR, UV-Visible, ESR spectroscopy and cyclic voltammetry. The geometrical parameters of these complexes were performed by DFT and TD-DFT methods. The theoretical calculations confirm that the vanadium(IV) center exhibited square pyramidal geometry in 1-4 and distorted octahedral geometry in 5. The paramagnetic resonance *g*-factor and the magnetic susceptibilities (magnetic moments) of vanadyl complexes are discussed. The complexes were also tested for their *in vitro* antidiabetic activity (α -glucosidase inhibition activity). The complexes exhibited moderate antidiabetic properties.

Keywords : Vanadium(IV) complexes, DFT and TD-DFT calculations, ESR (electron spin resonance), antidiabetic properties.

Introduction

Vanadium is an important trace metal of bioinorganic importance and is present in most of the organisms¹. The toxicity of vanadium is dependent on its oxidation state, with vanadium(V) being more toxic than vanadium(IV)². Vanadium is often taken up as vanadate, in pathway parallel to phosphate³. Vanadium(IV) compounds mimic most of the biological effects of insulin in various cell types. They have been shown to increase glucose transport and oxidation (by the lowering glucose level in blood), to stimulate glycogen synthesis and to inhibit hepatic gluconeogenesis. The antidiabetic effect is probably attained via irreversible strong inhibition of the insulin receptor, one of the large classes of tyrosine kinase receptors. Recently a number of synthetic vanadyl complexes as potential insulin mimetic agents have been reported⁴⁻⁸. A number of synthetic imidazole and pyridine based compounds of potential insulin-mimetic activity have been studied in solution^{9,10}.

In an attempt to obtain more insight into the bioactivity (antidiabetic activity properties) of vanadyl complexes,

we report herein the synthesis, characterization, DFT calculations and antidiabetic properties of some oxovanadium(IV) complexes with L-aspartic acid and imidazoles/1,10-phenanthroline as co-ligands. The complex structures have been characterized by magnetic, microanalyses and different spectral methods. The antidiabetic properties of these complexes have also been evaluated and discussed. All synthesized five complexes **1-5** show moderate α -glucosidase activity (antidiabetic properties). Therefore, these complexes may be proposed as model for antidiabetic agents (insulin mimetic agents) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Vanadium sulphate pentahydrate was procured from CDH. Aspartic acid and 2-methylimidazole were purchased from S. D. Fine Chemicals, India. Imidazole purchased from Sisco Chem Industries. Chemicals like 2-ethylimidazole (Acros), 2-methylbenzimidazole (Aldrich) and 1,10-phenanthroline (Thomas Backer) were purchased from chemicals industries as indicated in brackets. All

Scheme 1. α -Glycosidase (enzyme) model.

other chemicals used were of synthetic grade and used without further purification.

Complex **1** the salt $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.253 g, 1 mmol) was dissolved in 20 ml of methanol. Equimolar aspartic acid (0.133 g, 1 mmol) and imidazole (0.068 g, 1 mmol) were added and stirred continuously for 4–5 h. Blue coloured solution was obtained and the resulting coloured solution was filtered and dried and stored in CaCl_2 desiccators, at room temperature. Yield (%) : (75%), Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{V}$ ($M = 266.107$) (%) : C, 31.59; H, 3.41; N, 15.79. Found : C, 31.56; H, 3.40; N, 15.76.

Anal. Calcd. for complex **2** : $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{V}$ ($M = 280.13$) (%) : C, 34.30; H, 3.96; N, 15.01. Found : C, 34.32; H, 3.94; N, 15.10.

Anal. Calcd. for complex **3** : $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{V}$ ($M = 294.16$) (%) : C, 36.75; H, 4.45; N, 14.28. Found : C, 36.74; H, 4.44; N, 14.26.

Anal. Calcd. for complex **4** : $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{V}$ ($M = 330.19$) (%) : C, 36.75; H, 4.45; N, 14.28. Found : C, 36.74; H, 4.46; N, 12.26.

Anal. Calcd. for complex **5** : $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3\text{V}$ ($M = 378.23$) (%) : C, 50.81; H, 3.46; N, 11.11. Found : C, 50.79; H, 3.45; N, 11.12.

Elemental analyses of the complexes were performed on an Elemental Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer, School of Chemistry, University of Hyderabad. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was carried out with a BAS-100 Epsilon Electrochemical Analyzer having an electrochemical

cell with a three-electrode system. Ag/AgCl was used as reference electrode, glassy carbon as working electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode; 0.5 M TBAP (tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate) was used as supporting electrolyte and DMSO as solvent. All measurements were carried out at 298 K under nitrogen atmosphere. Magnetic measurements were performed by Guoy's method^{11,12} in room temperature. Sample tube were calibrated with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$. UV-Vis spectra were recorded at 25 °C on a Shimadzu-1601 spectrophotometer UV-160 in quartz cells. Infrared (IR) spectra were obtained by the KBr method using a Bruker Alpha-T model Fourier transform (FTIR) spectrophotometer (Bruker Instrument, Germany). The spectrophotometer was equipped with a Global IR source, KBr beam splitter and detector. For each spectrum, 16 scans were obtained with resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The spectra were processed by means of the program OPUS 7.0. Electron paramagnetic resonance (ESR) spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series ESR spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band of 100 kHz modulation frequency. Tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) was used as field marker ($g_e = 2.00277$). ESR measurements of oxovanadium(IV) complexes were recorded in DMSO at room temperature and at LNT from RSIC (SAIF) IIT, Bombay. The g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} values were measured according to the standard procedure¹³.

Method for determination of α -glucosidase was used as reported in literature¹⁴. Rat intestinal acetone powder (Sigma Chemicals, USA) was sonicated properly in normal saline (100 : 1 w/v) and after centrifugation at 3000 rpm \times 30 min the supernatant was treated as crude intestinal α -glucosidase. 50 μL various dilution in DMSO (0.1 mg/ml solution) were mixed and incubated for 50 μL of enzyme in a 96-well microplate for 5 min. Reaction mixture was further incubated for another 10 min with 50 μL substrate (5 mM, *p*-nitrophenyl- μ -D-glucopyranoside) prepared in 100 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) and release of nitrophenol was read at 405 nm spectrophotometrically (Multimode^{synergy}H4 microplate reader, BioTek Instrument, Inc., Winooski, VT, USA). All the samples were run in triplicate and acarbose was taken as standard reference compound. Several dilutions of primary solution (5 mg/ml DMSO) were made and assayed accordingly to obtain

concentration of the test sample required to inhibit 50% activity (IC_{50}) of the enzyme. Quantification was performed with respect to the standard curve of acarbose ($Y = 26.63X + 46.26$, $R^2 = 0.958$) and results were expressed as microgram of acarbose equivalent per ml of extract. Percent α -glucosidase inhibition was calculated using $(1 - B/A) \times 100$, where A is absorbance of reactants without test samples and B is absorbance of reactants with test samples.

3D Molecular modeling of one of the synthesized compounds is an interactive geometry optimization and molecular display. It has the ability to handle transition compounds. The input file of the complex prepared with Gauss View 5.0.9¹⁵. All the calculations were carried out with the Gaussian 09 Revision-D.01¹⁶ by using density functional theory (DFT) methods with Becker-3-Lee-Yang-Parr (B3LYP) hybrid exchange-correlation functional and the standard LANL2DZ basis set for the complexes. Molecular surface electrostatic potentials (MSEP), vibrational frequency calculations, bond lengths, bond angles, dihedral angles, natural population analysis and calculation of molecular energies, HOMO and LUMO were made. Frank-Condon electronic excitation spectra may be calculated on the basis of optimized structures both in vacuum and in DMSO as a solvent within the time dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) taking into account the lowest 30 excitation.

Results and discussion

The mixed ligand oxovanadium(IV) complexes **1-5** were prepared by taking equimolar ratio of vanadyl sulphate penta hydrate, L-aspartic acid and imidazole in methanol, according to the following equation :

where Aspa = L-aspartic acid, L = imidazole (ImH), 2-methylimidazole (2-mImH), 2-ethylimidazole (2-eImH), 2-methylbenzimidazole (2-mbenzImH) and 1,10-phenanthroline (1,10-phen). These complexes are soluble in DMSO and insoluble in other common organic solvents. The formulation of these complexes is based on their physico-chemical and theoretical studies. The formulations of all complexes are shown in Scheme 2.

Experimental FT-IR and theoretical derived from DFT method are shown in Fig. S1 and Fig. S2. Peaks of vanadyl complexes found in FT-IR are well correlated in theoretical IR spectra. The complexes of oxovanadium(IV) exhibit bands at 3398–3421 cm^{-1} and 3115–3149 cm^{-1} may be assigned to asymmetrical and symmetrical $\nu(NH/NH_2)$ stretching mode of the coordinated terminal amino group¹⁷. These $\nu(NH)$ mode at approximately 3100 cm^{-1} almost comparable to the uncoordinated amide nitrogen of the ligand, under this investigation are not taking part in coordination. Most of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes exhibit a strong band near 1000 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to $\nu(V=O)$ ¹⁸. In contrast, several oxovanadium(IV) complexes have been reported in which this stretching mode appears at quite lower wave numbers, around at 900 cm^{-1} . The shift of $\nu(V=O)$ band to lower wave numbers suggested due to the presence of a slight $\dots V=O \dots V=O \dots$ type interaction occurring between a vandyl oxygen of one molecule with a vanadium metal in another molecule. In all complexes, the $\nu(V=O)$ mode is found at 972–980 cm^{-1} thereby suggesting the absence of $\dots V=O \dots V=O \dots$ type interaction^{19,20}. A medium type of band was obtained at the range of 1711–1725 cm^{-1} due to the coordination of carboxylate group $\nu(C=O)$. All the complexes exhibit a strong band in the range of 607–638 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to $\nu(V-O)$ ²¹. Important IR spectral bands of the synthesized complexes are presented in Table S1.

The UV-Visible spectra were recorded in DMSO solution. These spectra generally consist of one or few broad absorption bands. All molecules can absorb radiation in the UV-Visible region because they contain electrons; both shared and unshared which can be excited to higher energy level. The wave length at which absorption occurs depends upon how firmly the electrons are tightly bound and radiation of high energy or short wave length is required for their excitation. The pertinent value of λ_{max} (nm) along with assignments is shown in Table 1. The intense high energy absorptions reasonably attributable to charge-transfer transitions, low energy absorption to essentially metal bonded d-d transitions. In complexes **1-4**, broad d-d bands are centered at 800 nm. LMCT at 300 nm originating from the lone pair in a *p*-orbital on the

Scheme 2. Synthetic route of complexes 1-5.

aspartic acid into an empty d -orbital of the vanadium ion. In the complex **5** the LMCT is observed as high energy LMCT band of compared to remaining complexes **1-4**. The representative experimental spectrum of complex **1**, **2**, **4** and complex **3**, **5** are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. S3 respectively and their theoretical UV spectrum of the complexes **1-5** are shown in Fig. S4. The spectral data showed

that in the low energy region of the spectrum the oxovanadium(IV) complexes displays three low-intensity bands. The bands from UV-Vis range are assigned to ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions respectively²². According to Ballhausen and others^{23,24}, these energy absorption bands are assigned to the ligand field transitions: $(d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}, d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ cor-

Table 1. Electronic peak assignments of ligand (Aspa) and complexes **1-5**

Ligand and complexes	Peak assignment
Ligand	300 $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
[VO(Aspa)(ImH)] (1)	350 $\pi \rightarrow \pi$ LMCT 510 $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) 790 $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$)
[VO(Aspa)(2-mimH)] (2)	390 $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ 580 $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) 800 a_1^* ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$)
[VO(Aspa)(2-eimH)] (3)	380 $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ 550 $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) 810 a_1^* ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$)
[VO(Aspa)(2-mbenzimidH)] (4)	375 $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ 590 $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) 800 a_1^* ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$)
[VO(Aspa)(1,10-phen)] (5)	380 $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ 565 $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) 770 a_1^* ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$)

Fig. 1. Experimental representation of UV of complexes **1, 2** and **4**.

responding to $b_2 \rightarrow e^*(v_1)$, $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*(v_2)$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1(v_3)$ transitions respectively in C_{4v} symmetry²⁵. These spectral characteristics suggest that the synthesized oxovanadium(IV) complexes **1-4** are five-coordinate, square-pyramidal structure²⁶⁻³². The spectrum of the complex **5** in DMSO exhibit two low intensity transitions, one at ~ 570 nm and another at ~ 770 nm and one high intensity bands at ~ 330 nm (LMCT). These transitions are consistent with distorted octahedral geometry commonly associated with spectrum of vanadyl ion and its complex, which can be as-

signed (from lowest to the highest energy) as the ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{2g}$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$), ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) and ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) transitions according to Ballhausen and Gray molecular orbital scheme³³. From theoretical data in **1**, three closely spaced, moderately intense bands at ~ 762 , ~ 548 and ~ 467 nm have been observed. The absorption band around ~ 762 nm are due to HUMO \rightarrow LUMO electronic excitations and these can be assigned to d-d transitions showing that the low energy closely spaced peaks are due to ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) transitions. The absorption band around ~ 548 nm is due to the HUMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 electronic excitations and these can be assigned to $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ d-d transition. The band at 467 nm appears to be a composition of excitation at 2.6502 eV and $f = 0.0017$ is due to the contribution of HUMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO transition. The TD-DFT calculated excitations and approximate assignments for ligand and other complexes are given in Table 2.

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded for complexes **1-5** one-step redox in DMSO at RT under nitrogen vs Ag/AgCl reference electrode at scan rate of 100 mV/s. Voltammograms consist of two well-separated peaks, one cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}) and one anodic peak potential (E_{pa}). The cathodic peak current (I_{pc}) is almost equal to the anodic peak current (I_{pa}). The employed potential range was (-2025 to $+800$ mV) in the presence of 0.5 M of tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as a supporting electrolyte. The obtained results of the complexes are presented in Table S2. The complexes of vanadyl sulphate exhibit one electron irreversible transfer process with a reduction peak at $E_{pc} = -762$ mV to -1828 mV and corresponding peak at $E_{pa} = -600$ mV to -650 mV. These five complexes showed redox couples with peak to peak separation values (ΔE_p) ranging from 112 to 1208 mV, indicating a single step one electron process.

The negative E^0 potentials -706 to -1239 mV may be assigned to the conversion^{34,35} of V^{IV} to V^{III} . With the increasing scan rates, ΔE_p giving further evidence for the irreversible V^{IV}/V^{III} couple. The electrochemical behaviour of **1-5** are shown in Fig. 2. The reduction at ~ -1.8 V is believed to be due to the vanadium(IV) \rightarrow vanadium(III) couple, with a small pressure at ~ -0.75 V probably due to a vanadium(IV) reduction. The oxidation

Table 2. TD-DFT calculated excitations and approximate assignments

Excitation energy (eV) Ligand (Aspa)	Wavelength (nm)	Oscillator strength (f)	Composition (%)
3.9832	311.27	0.0000	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (81%)
4.1759	296.91	0.0012	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (57%)
4.4555	278.27	0.0000	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (36%)
4.8301	256.69	0.0000	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 3 (13%)
4.8728	254.44	0.0008	α HOMO-2 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (9%)
4.9428	250.84	0.0000	α HOMO-3 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 2 (8%)
Complex 1			
1.6252	762.89	0.0005	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (81%)
2.2600	548.61	0.0004	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 1 (57%)
2.6502	467.83	0.0017	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (36%)
3.2736	378.74	0.0002	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 3 (13%)
3.5743	346.88	0.0000	α HOMO-2 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (9.61%)
3.7557	330.12	0.0004	α HOMO-3 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 2 (8.22%)
Complex 2			
1.1350	1092.41	0.0006	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (53%)
1.7303	716.55	0.0002	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 2 (79%)
2.4470	506.68	0.0021	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 2 (46%)
2.4963	496.67	0.0009	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 1 (30%)
2.6927	460.45	0.0004	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (54%)
2.9346	422.48	0.0002	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 1 (22%)
Complex 3			
-0.4615	1105.56	0.0000	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (64%)
-0.0816	1080.21	0.0000	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (61%)
0.2799	965.90	0.0009	α HOMO-2 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (4.88%)
0.3711	756.17	0.0002	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (20%)
0.5921	510.84	0.0009	α HOMO-2 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (89%)
0.7372	490.87	0.0020	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 1 (10%)
Complex 4			
1.0705	1158.17	0.0130	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (10%)
1.8149	683.15	0.0149	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (81%)
2.2165	559.36	0.0012	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 1 (14%)
2.2598	548.64	0.0061	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 2 (7%)
2.3503	527.53	0.0006	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (14%)
2.4316	509.89	0.0005	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 5 (33%)
Complex 5			
0.9646	1285.28	0.0003	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO (61%)
1.1393	1088.22	0.0001	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 1 (45%)
1.4927	830.61	0.0001	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 3 (12%)
1.5957	776.97	0.0001	α HOMO-1 $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 4 (34%)
2.1322	581.49	0.0002	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 5 (36%)
2.2582	549.03	0.0012	α HOMO $\rightarrow\alpha$ LUMO + 2 (80%)

peak at ~ -0.75 V has increased in size. Furthermore, an initial positive scan shows this peak on the first cycle, indicating that it is the primary reduction product. The reactions based on reductions of **1-5** may be given as :

The proposed reactions are based on similar suggested by Neal and Murray³⁶. Similar electrochemical behaviour of VO(acac)₂ has been studied by two groups^{37,38}. The deviation of I_{pa}/I_{pc} from **1** (Table S2) in the present complexes suggest that the redox couple is irreversible ($\Delta E_p > 100$ mV). This may be due to one electron transfer reaction.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of complexes **1-5**.

The observed magnetic moments of the synthesized complexes are given in Table S3. Oxovanadium(IV) belonging to the $3d^1$ $S = 1/2$ ³⁹. The magnetically dilute oxovanadium(IV) complexes usually exhibit magnetic moments to their spin only value of 1.73 B.M. At room temperature, the observed values of the magnetic moment of the complexes are in the range of 1.71–1.77 B.M., as expected for magnetically dilute oxovanadium(IV)

complexes⁴⁰ and which correspond to a single electron of the $3d^1$ system of square-pyramidal oxovanadium(IV).

ESR is a useful tool in investigating the nature of the bonding in oxovanadium(IV) complexes⁴¹. The X-band ESR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO solution at room temperature (25 °C) and as a Frozen glassy state at 77 K. The calculated ESR parameters are given in Table 3. The room temperature spectra in DMSO exhibit eight line patterns typical of oxovanadium(IV) ($I = 7/2$), which indicates that a single vanadium(IV) is present in the molecule, that is the monomeric structure of the complexes. Thus, isotropic ESR spectrum of a magnetically dilute oxovanadium(IV) complexes gives $(2 \times 7/2 + 1)$ 8 lines. The X-band ESR spectra of the complexes **1** and **2** in 100% DMSO at LNT is shown in Fig. S5. Similar to the spectra of many other oxovanadium(IV) complexes^{42,43} the spectrum exhibits an axially symmetrical signal of tetravalent vanadium, split into a number of hyperfine lines which originates from the d^1 electron interaction with nuclear spin $I = 7/2$. The spectra display well-resolved V ($I = 7/2$) hyperfine lines ($g_{||} > g_{\perp}$) and

Table 3. ESR parameters of the complexes **1-5** in 100% DMSO

Complexes	Room temperature (RT)		Liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT)			
	g_{iso}	A_{iso} (G)	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	$A_{ }$ (G)	A_{\perp} (G)
1	2.0227	92	1.980	1.960	185	80
2	2.0801	85	2.088	2.079	180	75
3	2.0160	95	2.183	2.094	190	85
4	2.010	105	2.014	2.001	195	95
5	2.0265	95	1.9312	2.0326	183	78

derived parameters ($g_{||} = 1.9312$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.0326$) obtained from spectra are given in Table 3. The frozen DMSO solution spectrum of **5** gave the ESR parameters with $g_{\perp} = 2.0326 > g_{||} = 1.9321$; $A_{||} = 183\text{G} > A_{\perp} = 78\text{G}$; $A_{iso} = 95\text{G}$; $g_{iso} = 2.0265$. These values fit well with those of the reported values of VO²⁺ which have slightly distorted octahedral coordination⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸. It is clear that the g values obtained are indicative for the presence of vanadyl ions (VO²⁺) in a distorted octahedrally coordinated environment. The various bond lengths, bond angles and di-

hedral angles generated from the optimized structure of the complex **1** is given in the Table 4 (for complexes **2-5** for Tables S3-S6). The computed bond lengths such as V(1)-O(2), V(1)-O(2), V(1)-N(4), V(1)-O(11), V(1)-N(14) in the present complex (**1**) are 1.6368 (Å), 1.8481 (Å), 1.8977 (Å), 1.871 (Å), 1.9 (Å) respectively. The significant computed bond angles (in °) are as : O(2)-V(1)-N(4) (91.0613), O(2)-V(1)-O(11) (164.0861), N(4)-V(1)-O(9) (105.3131), N(4)-V(1)-N(14) (138.2213), O(9)-V(1)-N(14) (116.0403), O(2)-V(1)-O(9) (102.1915), O(2)-V(1)-N(14) (86.0826), N(4)-V(1)-O(11) (88.2955), O(9)-V(1)-O(11) (93.3022), O(11)-V(1)-N(14) (83.8397) respectively. These results are comparable to the data reported elsewhere⁴⁹. The significant dihedral angles (in °) such as : O(2)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5) (-156.9232), O(2)-V(1)-N(4)-H(24) (84.4806), O(9)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23) (66.5134), O(11)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5) (38.9825), O(2)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23) (-36.4344), O(9)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5) (-53.9753), O(9)-V(1)-N(4)-H(24) (-

172.5716), O(11)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23) (159.4713) respectively and suggest that the square pyramidal structure of the complex.

The optimized molecular structures of the complexes **1-5** are shown in Fig. 3.

Quantitatively, the angular structural parameter τ proposed by Addison *et al.*⁵⁰ may also be used to distinguish between TB and SP structures, evaluated as $\tau = \beta - \alpha / 60$, where α and β are the largest bond angles, O(2)-V(1)-N(4) and O(2)-V(1)-O(9), respectively, taking $\beta \geq \alpha$. Here $\beta = 102.1915$ and $\alpha = 91.0613$. For purely SP polyhedra, τ is 0 and for a perfect TB polyhedron τ is 1. Corman *et al.*⁵¹ applied this parameter and described vanadyl complexes with $0 < \tau < 0.5$ as distorted SP, while complexes with $0.5 < \tau < 1$ were considered as distorted TB. Computationally, it is found that $\tau = 0.185$ for [VO(L-Aspa)(ImH)], confirming SP geometry. HOMO and LUMO very important parameters⁵² for chemical re-

Table 4. Geometrical parameters bond lengths (Å), bond angles (°) and dihedral angles (°) of complex **1**

Bond length (Å)			
V(1)-O(2)	1.6368	V(1)-O(2)	1.8481
V(1)-N(4)	1.8977	V(1)-O(11)	1.871
V(1)-N(14)	1.9		
Bond angle (°)			
O(2)-V(1)-N(4)	91.0613	O(2)-V(1)-O(9)	102.1915
O(2)-V(1)-O(11)	164.0861	O(2)-V(1)-N(14)	86.0826
N(4)-V(1)-O(9)	105.3131	N(4)-V(1)-O(11)	88.2955
N(4)-V(1)-N(14)	138.2213	O(9)-V(1)-O(11)	93.3022
O(9)-V(1)-N(14)	116.0403	O(11)-V(1)-N(14)	83.8397
Dihedral angle (°)			
O(2)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5)	-156.9232	O(2)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23)	-36.4344
O(2)-V(1)-N(4)-H(24)	84.4806	O(9)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5)	-53.9753
O(9)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23)	66.5134	O(9)-V(1)-N(4)-H(24)	-172.5716
O(11)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5)	38.9825	O(11)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23)	159.4713
O(11)-V(1)-N(4)-H(24)	-79.6138	N(14)-V(1)-N(4)-C(5)	117.7703
N(14)-V(1)-N(4)-H(23)	-121.741	N(14)-V(1)-N(4)-H(24)	-0.826
O(2)-V(1)-O(9)-C(7)	97.4114	N(4)-V(1)-O(9)-C(7)	2.8915
O(11)-V(1)-O(9)-C(7)	-86.2438	N(14)-V(1)-O(9)-C(7)	-170.9972
O(2)-V(1)-O(11)-C(3)	-107.032	N(4)-V(1)-O(11)-C(3)	-19.1403
O(9)-V(1)-O(11)-C(3)	86.1038	N(14)-V(1)-O(11)-C(3)	-158.0434
O(2)-V(1)-N(14)-C(15)	-172.8105	O(2)-V(1)-N(14)-C(18)	6.2067
N(4)-V(1)-N(14)-C(15)	-85.6066	N(4)-V(1)-N(14)-C(18)	93.4106
O(9)-V(1)-N(14)-C(15)	85.5278	O(9)-V(1)-N(14)-C(18)	-95.455

Fig. 3. Optimized structures of the complexes 1-5.

action. One can determine the way the molecule interact with other species. Hence they are called frontier orbitals. The HOMO is the orbital that primarily acts as an electron donor and the LUMO is the orbital that largely acts as the electron acceptor, and the gap between HOMO and LUMO characterizes the molecular stability⁵³. Four important molecular orbitals, second highest [HOMO-1], and highest occupied MO's [HOMO], the lowest [LUMO], second lowest unoccupied MO's [LUMO+1], was found for complex 1 and the observed energies in the same order are as -0.26644 au, -0.24106 au, -0.08239 au and -0.05905 au. While the energy gap between [HOMO] [LUMO] and [HOMO-1] [LUMO+1] are as -0.15867 au and -0.20739 au respectively. The presence of one un-

paired electron in the [HOMO] justifies that it is paramagnetic with a singly occupied molecular orbital (SOMO).

The energy of the frontier orbitals for molecules in terms of ionization energy (IE) and electron affinity (EA) of the complex 1 from Koopmans's theorem⁵⁴ are :

$$-E_{\text{HOMO}} = \text{IE} \quad (\text{i})$$

$$-E_{\text{LUMO}} = \text{EA} \quad (\text{ii})$$

The absolute electronegativity (χ_{abs}) and absolute hardness (η) are related to IA and EA⁵⁵ as given below :

$$\chi_{\text{abs}} = (\text{IE} + \text{EA})/2 = (E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}})/2 \quad (\text{iii})$$

$$\eta = (\text{IE} - \text{EA})/2 = (E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}})/2 \quad (\text{iv})$$

Hard molecules have a large HOMO-LUMO gap and soft

molecules have a small HOMO-LUMO gap⁵⁶. The absolute electronegativity (χ_{abs}) and absolute hardness (η) complex calculated using eqs. (iii) and (iv) are provided in Table S8. There is a very short energy gap between HOMO→LUMO and HOMO-1→LUMO+1 in ligand -0.1926 au and -0.25851 au respectively. The energy difference of HOMO→LUMO and HOMO-1→LUMO+1 is -0.14386 au, -0.16586 au, -0.0439 au, -0.10092 au, -

0.0791 au, -0.11688 au, -0.0746 au and -0.13102 au for **2-5**, respectively. HOMO and LUMO orbital are closely related to each other. The HOMO-LUMO structures with energy-level diagram of complex **1** is shown in Fig. 4 (ligand (Aspa)) and complexes **2-5** are shown in Fig. S6-S10). Another important property related to the dipole moment and hardness is electrophilicity index (ω) and

Fig. 4. HOMO-LUMO structure with energy level diagram of complex **1**.

global softness (S), shown in equation below. The values of ω and S are

$$\omega = \mu^2/2\eta \quad (\text{v})$$

$$S = 1/\eta \quad (\text{vi})$$

Absolute electronegativity (χ_{abs}) and absolute hardness (η), electrophilicity index (ω) and global softness (S) of vanadium(IV) complexes and ligand are shown in Table S8. DFT has been used to calculate the dipole moment (μ), mean polarizability (α) and the total first static hyperpolarizability (β_0)^{57,58} for the vanadium(IV) complexes in terms of x, y and z from the following equations.

$$\mu = (\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + \mu_z^2)/2 \quad (\text{vii})$$

$$\alpha = 1/3 (\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy} + \alpha_{zz}) \quad (\text{viii})$$

$$\Delta\alpha = [(\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy})^2 + (\alpha_{yy} - \alpha_{zz})^2 + (\alpha_{zz} - \alpha_{xx})^2/2]^{1/2} \quad (\text{ix})$$

$$\beta_0 = (\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2 + \beta_z^2)^{1/2} \quad (\text{x})$$

$$\text{and } \beta_x = \beta_{xxx} + \beta_{xyy} + \beta_{xzz}$$

$$\beta_y = \beta_{yyy} + \beta_{yzz} + \beta_{yyz}$$

$$\beta_z = \beta_{zzz} + \beta_{xxz} + \beta_{yyz}$$

or

$$\beta_0 = [(\beta_{xxx} + \beta_{xyy} + \beta_{xzz})^2 + (\beta_{yyy} + \beta_{yzz} + \beta_{yyz})^2 + (\beta_{zzz} + \beta_{xxz} + \beta_{yyz})^2]^{1/2} \quad (\text{xi})$$

The calculated electric dipole moment μ (Debye), isotopic polarisability α (in au), anisotropy of the polarisability $\Delta\alpha$ (in au) and all hyperpolarisability (β) components (in au) values are given in Table S9. Calculated all (μ , β and α) components (μ , α) total and (β_0 , $\Delta\alpha$) of the ligand (Aspa) and complexes **1-5** are given in Table S9.

The natural atomic charges of vanadium(IV) complexes obtained by NBO and Mulliken population and spin density analysis⁵⁹ with B3LYP/LANL2DZ basis set are compared in Tables S10-S15 for ligand (Aspa) and complex **1-5**. The pictorial form of spin density of the complexes **1-5** is given in Fig. 5. The comparison between Mulliken net charges and the atomic natural ones is not an easy task, since the theoretical background of the two methods is very different. Looking at the results there are surprising differences the Mulliken and NBO charges. The data indicating that O(2), O(8), O(9), O(10), O(11), N(4),

N(14), N(17) and C(5), C(6), C(15), C(16) bears negative values both in Mulliken and NBO analyses. C(3), C(7), C(18) and H(12), H(13), H(19), H(20), H(21), H(22), H(23), H(24), H(25) have positive values. V(1) also bears positive values in NBO analyses as well as in Mulliken analyses but their spin densities are not same of the complex **1**. The colour range in the scale of the positive and negative charge and graphical representation for NBO atomic charge are Mulliken charges and spin density of the complexes shown in Fig. 5. These are clearly shown in the graphical representation of NBO and Mulliken charges and their spin density of the ligand and complexes **1-5** are given in the Figs. S11-S16. The definition of Mulliken charges is based on population analysis. The Mulliken population analysis provides a partitioning of either the total charge density or an orbital density. The number of electrons in the molecule (N) is the integral of the charge density over space. N is partitioned for all atoms, considering also the overlap population. According to theory, the overlap population of atoms A and B is divided between the two atoms in half-to-half ratio. This is one weak point of the theory. The other weak point is its strong dependence on the basis set applied. The atomic net charge is the difference between the calculated number of electrons belonging to the atom in the complex and the number of electrons of the isolated atom. The natural atomic charge is based on the theory of the natural population analysis. The analysis is carried out with NBO. They are linear combinations of the natural atomic orbitals. The derivation of a valence shell atomic orbital (NAO) involves diagonalization of the localized block of the full density matrix of a given molecule associated with basic functions on that atom. A distinguishing feature of NAOs is that they meet the simultaneous requirement of orthonormality and maximum occupancy. In a polyatomic molecule, the NAOs mostly retain one-center character, and thus they are optimal for describing the molecular electron density around each atomic center. Natural bond orbitals are linear combinations of the NAOs of two bonded atoms. The natural population analysis satisfies Pauli's exclusion principle and solves the basis set dependence problem of the Mulliken population analysis⁶⁰.

Fig. 5. Spin density representation of complexes 1-5.

The complexation behaviour of the ligand was analyzed by MESP surface diagram is used to understand the reactive behaviour of a ligand, in that negative regions can be regarded as nucleophilic centers, whereas the positive regions are potential electrophilic sites. The MESP⁶¹ mapped surface of the ligand and all the vanadyl complexes **1-5** is given in Fig. 6. In vanadium complexes the coordination environment of three oxygen and two nitrogen atom is the region of most negative potential. The electron rich red regions between three oxygen and two nitrogen atom are theoretically potential active sides of the ligand to positively charged metals as expected. Predominance of green region in the MESP surface corresponds to potential halfway between the two extremes red and dark blue colour.

α -Glucosidase inhibition data (percentage inhibition at 200 μ g and IC_{50} values) for oxovanadium(IV) complexes have been obtained and presented in Table 5. The results of inhibition of α -glucosidase by oxovanadium(IV) complexes at various concentrations are also presented graphically in Fig. 7. A perusal of the data reveals the following points :

- (1) Vanadyl sulphate itself is a poor α -glucosidase inhibitor; all the complexes show much higher inhibition.
- (2) All oxovanadium(IV) complexes show much stronger α -glucosidase inhibition as these are stronger α -glucosidase inhibitors.
- (3) In the complexes of vanadyl sulphate, **1** and **3** show nearly similar inhibition behaviour ($IC_{50} = 43.67$

Fig. 6. Molecular electrostatic potential (MESP) of ligand (Aspa) and complexes 1-5.

Table 5. α -Glucosidase inhibition by the oxovanadium(IV) complexes 1-5

Complexes	% Inhibition at 200 (μ g)	IC ₅₀ (μ g/ml)
1	74.89	43.67
2	88.31	73.55
3	68.72	45.32
4	83.27	56.78
5	78.23	76.22
Acarbose	–	23.67

and 45.32 μ g) and the **2** and **5** also show nearly similar inhibition behaviour (IC₅₀ = 73.55 and 76.22 μ g) and **4** have average value (IC₅₀ = 56.78 μ g) among of these complexes. As **1** and **3** are strongest inhibitors, **2** and **5** are weakest inhibitors. **1** is strongest inhibitor than other due to five coordinated vanadium and less steric hindrance. Similarly **5** is weakest inhibitor due to six coordination of vanadium and hence provide no site (vacant) for α -glucosidase.

Fig. 6. Graph between concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) and absorbance for complexes 1-5.

In Table 5, % inhibition at 200 μg of oxovanadium(IV) complex 2 has higher value as compared to other complexes of this series but IC_{50} of this complex is lower.

One would normally expect that if the value of % inhibition at 200 μg was high the IC_{50} values should be low. Higher value of % inhibition however, does not necessarily lead to lower value of IC_{50} . If the inhibitor concentration vs % inhibition curves have different nature and cross each other, it may be reverse. For oxovanadium(IV) complexes as inhibitors, α -glucosidase may coordinate to the central vanadium ion at sixth (vacant) coordination position of the five coordinated vanadium(IV) complex. Cornman *et al.*⁶² have earlier suggested formation of such a bond between the metal ion and protein side chain for inhibition or activation of the enzymes.

Conclusion

A series 1-5 of mixed ligand oxovanadium(IV) complexes were synthesized and characterized using various physico-chemical techniques. From magnetic moment values, ESR and electronic spectra, these complexes found to have a distorted square pyramidal 1-4 and distorted octahedral 5 geometry around central metal ion. These complexes show irreversible redox chemistry as measured by cyclic voltammetry. Molecular structures of these complexes have been established by quantum mechanical cal-

culations (DFT method). Catalytic activity (antidiabetic activity) have also been measured and discussed.

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